

EMIT

Data Compression and Cloud Screening using a High-Performance Embedded System-on-a-Chip for the Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) imaging spectrometer on the International Space Station (ISS)

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8th International Workshop on On-Board Payload Data Compression (OBPDC 2022)
September 28-30, 2022

Content

- Introduction to Alpha Data
- Relevant Spectrometry background, and the EMIT and Mission
- EMIT operations, dataflow and processing
- The FPIE-D's implementation
- EMIT in action!
- Time for questions, hopefully!

Who is Alpha Data? EMIT is a JPL Project

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Let's assume that JPL does not need in introduction...

ALPHA DATA

- Est. 1993 (nearly 30-y/o)
- SMC, ~30 employees.
- Locations: Edinburgh UK (AD Ltd.) & Littleton, CO. USA. (AD Inc.)
- Certified Xilinx Alliance Partners and involved in the Xilinx Early Access Programs
- Core business: Designing COTS FPGA boards, including SDKs, and supporting customers.
- Designing high-end FPGA boards, since the first Virtex FPGAs.
- Extended services, offering MCOTS, custom board design and other FPGA design NRE services.
- Core markets: Embedded A&D, Data Centre/HPC, and Space
 - (new to space market in the last 5 years with the introduction of our KU-060 SDEV-KIT)
 - **Why are we here today: Key contributor to the EMIT, designing the FPIE-D component (and fabricating it's prototypes), and making significant contributions to the FPGA firmware and software**

EMIT Background and Mission

Imaging Spectroscopy Offers a Tested Approach to Measure Surface Mineralogy

Calibrated Image Cube

Material Map

1000s of Parallel Spectrometers

Direction of flight

Spectrometer & Telescope

Space

Airborne

Ground

Science Objective

Close the gap in our understanding of mineral dust heating or cooling of the Earth by determining the mineralogy of soils in the arid dust source regions and provide as inputs to Earth System models which determines the heating or cooling effect.

Mineral Dust and the Earth System

The earth has a mineral dust cycle with many impacts throughout the Earth system. Knowledge of dust source mineral composition is poor and needed to better understand current and future impacts.

Global Arid Land Mineral Composition

Mineral Dust Emission

Arid Dust Source Regions

Updated Earth System Models to Assess Radiative Forcing

The soil mineralogy dataset and model employed has a strong impact on the derived net direct radiative effects (DREs) of dust. This degree of uncertainty in the net DRE of dust constitutes an important gap in our understanding of the role it plays in climate.

Additional Value from EMIT spectroscopy

- Methane and CO2
- Biodiversity and Ecosystems
- Fire fuels and burn severity
- Hazards
- Geology and Resources
- Surface Plastic
- Algal blooms
- Agriculture
- Mid-Lat snow/ice

EMIT Instrument and Focal Plane Interface Electronics-Digital (FPIE-D)

EMIT Instrument

- NASA Class C Mission
- Mass Instrument: 188 kg
- Operational Power Average: 140 W
Peak: 179 W
- ISS Data average Rate CBE: 3.2 Mbps
(Peak 10Mbps)

FPIE-D Key Interface and functions

- Power control via **PCE** and **PSU**
- Cryocooler control via **HP-LCCE**
- Focal Plane Array control via **FPIE-A** LVDS data over 16 lanes from 8 ADCs of FPA at 1.6Gbit/sec
- Heaters Open-Loop and Closed-Loop digital control mode and temperature house keeping via **ATOM**
- Current and Voltage housekeeping via **PITB**
- Software Control of EMIT
- On-board data storage through SSDR
- Science data compression
- CMD & TLM with ISS over 1553
- Science Data Downlink over Ethernet with ISS (3.5 Mbps average; 10 Mbps peak)

FPIE-D Assembly

SpaceVPX Backplane PWB

FPIE-D processor PWB

Instrument mounted on Vibration Plate

Avionics mounted on Electronics Mounting Plate

Focal Plane Interface Electronics Digital (FPIE-D)

How does EMIT operate?

EMIT Operations Concept

- **Input Data Rate from Focal Plane Array (FPA):**
 - 1.6Gbps
- **Two data rate bottlenecks:**
 - ISS transfer: 0.003 Gbps
 - Compression: 0.37Gbps
- **By providing Non-Volatile Memory and splitting acquisition, processing, and downlink in to separate phases we can work around these bottlenecks.**

- Day-side science data collection occurs over the orbit day side.
 - They can vary in duration between 35 seconds up to about 11 minutes
 - Typical operations include between 0 and 23 science observations per orbit (one orbit == ~90-93 mins)
- EMIT does not have on-board calibration source and relies on dark calibrations science collection.

Series of consecutive orbits showing typical activities with acquisitions of Earth Coverage Science Target

Instrument Designs: EMIT FPIE-D Science Data Flow

Fast Lossless Extended (FLEX) data compression

- Provides to EMIT an expected lossless compression ratio 4:1 (compared to 14 bit samples obtained after co-adding and dropping 3 least significant bits) and a total compression throughput of 21 MSamples/sec. Both the compression ratio and throughput performance are needed to accommodate the limited size of the on-board storage (SSDR) and ISS Ethernet downlink rate.
- FLEX is a low-complexity compression algorithm designed specifically for lossless and near-lossless compression of multi/hyper spectral imagery. It is based on Fast Lossless (FL) compressor developed in JPL Section 332 and implemented on FPGA by JPL Section 349, which now forms the basis of CCSDS recommended standards 123.0-B-1 (Lossless) and 123.0-B-2 (Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless) for multi- and hyperspectral imagery.
- On EMIT, each FLEX compression FPGA core operates on one '1280 cross-track pixels x 328 spectral band X 32' co-added images (a "frame") at a time. Acquired frames are '1280 cross track pixels x 328 bands X 64 lines'.

Co-adding

- To avoid risk of saturation of the Focal Plane Array during acquisition, the signal from each two consecutive lines are co-added along the cross tracks.

Cloud Detection and Screening

- EMIT is expected to see approximately 42% of the acquisitions be obscured by clouds that need to be removed from the data, as compressing and downlinking it would be a waste of downlink bandwidth.
- Cloud Detection and Screening tests each pixel (consisting of 328 bands) against a five channel thresholds to determine whether the pixel is cloudy. Any frame of co-added images that is determined to be more than 50% cloudy is then excised by skipping compression, and only writing a small informational header that that image was cloud to the low speed partition on the SSDR.
- The channel thresholds and the bands are programmable. The initial thresholds are based on data collected by JPL's AVIRIS and AVIRIS-NG airborne hyperspectral instruments.

FLEX is a predictive compressor with a closed-loop quantization step that allows either lossless or near-lossless compression

(R: 860nm G: 660nm B:450nm)

Courtesy of D. Thompson

How was the FPIE-D
designed and built?

COTS to Space Transformation

Fast FPIE-D hardware/firmware/software development (2.5 years) was achieved by

- by basing the design on an existing COTS product: re-spinning to be suitable for Space (replacing component with Space Grade equivalent where needed) and extended it by adding features needed for the mission (e.g. 1553 interface)
- The COTS board that project was based on was used for a low-cost bread board solution allowing on day 1, SW/FPGA development work on real hardware, and more engineers to access hardware that was similar to the final board.

**Alpha Data COTS Zynq7000 board
in a XMC form factor**

**EMIT FPIE-D
EMIT's board is a flexible design not specific to EMIT**

COTS Space SSSDR Hardware

SSDR Block Diagram

- **TRL-9** (several on orbit)
- 3U VPX form-factor
- 440 GB host capacity
- 4-Lane SRIO interface
- 1160 MBytes/s data rate
- 30 Krad(Si) TID
- Radiation-Tolerant Flash RTG4 FPGA
- Design with rad-tolerant devices, except NAND
- 8-bit Reed Solomon ECC, 6 corrections

Every bus operation (Read or Write) has 28 host data bytes and 12 ECC bytes. Full correction for up to 6 failing bytes/devices

FPIE-D & SSSDR

Heart of the FPIE-D board: Zynq7K (XQ7100)

- Zynq-7000, ~10 years mature (first generation of Xilinx SoC*)
- They are complicated parts, and are very flexible.
- Notable features of interest:
 - SoC **integrating FPGA fabric** closely with CPU
 - **800MHz** Dual* Core ARM – Loads of CPU cycles
 - **Memory management unit** – Allow separations of processes
 - **DMA Engines** – Offloads data movement from CPU
 - **Large FPGA** - (compared to most space FPGAs).

- **SoCs are the future of AMD Xilinx FPGA. See MPSoC, and Versal ACAPs**
 - Larger ARM cores, VLIW-SIMD processing arrays (up to 400 cores), FPGA fabric, and more.
- **SoCs and their complexity is the new normal for AMD Xilinx FPGAs** (for Space as well as other apps.)
 - With the complex nature of these chips you **need to trust 3rd party code and tools**: Operating systems, drivers, BSPs, high-level compilers / code generators, IPs blocks, and “wizards” etc. to reduce development time
 - Every few years there are going to be new generations of these complicated chips with varying architectures where software and firmware components from previous generation should be portable to other hardware targets enabling keeping pace new generations of hardware.

Zynq Programmable Logic (PL) and Processing System (PS)

- FPGA design is divided into modules, each concerned with a single task, each is controlled by register access from software running on the ARM core(s).
- Data flows through and around the design, steered by SW control via the registers.
- Interrupts are used from the PL to signal software threads when operations complete or they are ready for a new task

- ➡ Data Acquisition
- ➡ Data Compression
- ➡ Data downlink

For cheap development

Application Flight Software Architecture

3 Main Layers:

- Application Layer
- Driver and OS Layer
- Hardware Layer

Application Layer:

- **Application FSW High Level** let separate mission specific code from control of hardware
- **Hardware Abstraction Layer** let us swich operating system, or target board.

Drivers separate kernel code from application code

Hardware Layer is implemented in the FPGA and on the board

- Threading philosophy is based on cooperative multi-tasking
- Main processing pipeline defined with modular threads.
 - Each class housing a thread, is either a Source, a Sink, or a Source and a Sink.
 - Any* source can be attached to any sink.
- Each thread performs one tasks on the pipeline – remember it’s not really performing the task, just steering the data (the FPGA does the hard work so the thread can sleep most of the time).
- With this architecture we can modify the state of the pipeline dynamically without re-compiling the application.
- The AFW is designed to run as a Virtual Process (RTP in VxWorks)*
- Provides protection from self, and to the Kernel.
- Something goes wrong, kill the RTP, and restart it. (This will clean up all the memory, and threads safely, restart the application, and reconfigure the FPGA design).

Multi Partition Recorder (MPR) API and SSSDRDMA IP

- Design IP to talk to SSSDR and Design MPR API providing simple file system to interact with the drive.
- The disk is split into 2 partitions treated as circular buffers
- Partition are presented to the users with 4 access methods, write, read, erase, and traverse meta data entries.
 - Writes are appending operations adding to the Data stored in the partition.
 - Reads can be to any part of the valid Data in the partition.
 - Erases are always from the start of the oldest Data.
- This looks like a file that can be appended to, has a seek-able read pointer, and can be truncated from the start of.
- As space is freed from erases, it becomes available for writing to due to the circular nature of its implementation (limits max size).
- Partition has option to auto erase when full.

Lift Off – EMIT in action

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EMIT: Launch, Docking, and Installation (14, 16, 24 July 2022)

SpaceX ISS Commercial Resupply Service (CRS-25) to ISS

SpaceX Cargo Dragon

SpaceX Dragon CRS-25 Cargo Ship Docks to ISS

ELC-2 DC1/MLM SM MRM1/2 ELC-3

ELC-4 Columbus-EPF ELC-1 JEM-EF

EMIT is installed on ELC-1

ISS Robotics removing from Dragon trunk and installing EMIT

FPIE-D Acquisition, Processing and downlink : Status

File Size Histogram of compressed data from low Speed Partition (8/13/2022 to 9/5/2022) over 200974 frames (10.8 TeraBytes Raw Data Acquired and Processed, 1.4 TeraBytes Data donwlink and 4.2 TeraBytes of Science Data on the ground) and over 22.5 days

10.8TB Captured -> Cloud Screen/CoAdd + Compress -> 1.4TB Download -> Decompress on Ground -> 4.2TB of Science Data!

Science and Dark (average compression ratio: 3.40:1) (1,000,000 to 22,000,000 Bytes)

Conclusion: EMIT First Light in Western Australia 28 July 2022 02:51 UTC

and acquired hyperspectral images (blue squares) up to August 21, 2022

EMIT Clouds Screening Scene (in block in the image) in Kazakhstan – 10 August 2022 10:13 UTC

EMIT Dust Source Region in Saudi Arabia – 10 August 2022 05:13 UTC (image swath is 80 km)

One small blue square: 60x60km 1280x1280 hyper-spectral pixels

EMIT First Image Cube of Radiance Spectra - 28 July 2022 02:51 UTC : The dark eucalyptus forests crossing the center of the image include the Julimar State Forest and the Avon Valley National Park in Western Australia

EMIT First Radiance Spectra - 28 July 2022 02:51 UTC. Calibrated radiance spectra that reveal the full set of expected surface and atmospheric features. EMIT measures the spectral range from 380 to 2500 nm for every point in the image

Thank you to all who have supported this journey!

FPIE-D

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Time for questions ...

Backup Slides

Alpha Data FPIE-D processor Assembly (ADM-CUST-EMIT-7Z5) with test fixture : 16 Layers (280 mm by 165 mm)

Alpha Data FPIE-D backplane Assembly (AD-VPX3_EMIT-BKP)

FPIE-D Status and Capability

Successfully flight qualification (2.5 years)

- No PWB respin for Prototype, EM and FM: only a few haywires needed
- Avionics TVAC (Nov. 2021): “Day in the Life” script emulating 40 orbits: processed 1.2TB raw data and downlink 0.2TB compressed data) during continuous operation for 4 days (emulate in-orbit operations)
- Instrument TVAC (Feb.-Mar. 2022): “Radiometric Calibration”, “FPA investigation” scripts: processed 3.6TB raw data and downlink 0.66TB compressed data during continuous operation for 7 days
- Ship from JPL to KSC: Tuesday March 15, 2022
- Launch Data: SpaceX ISS Commercial Resupply Service (CRS-25) using SpaceX Cargo Dragon 2 C208 S/C with Falcon 9 rocket, Tuesday June 7th, 2022

March 3-4 TVAC4 B noise time series

- **Cooldown of FPA from +23degC to -117degC**

Courtesy of D. Thompson

FPIE-D capabilities

- **Data acquisition at 1.6 Gbits/sec**
- **Lossless data compression ratio 4:1** to reduce on board data storage and increase science data return. Also capable of near-lossless compression.
- **Fast data compression (21 MSamples/sec)** to reduce on board data storage
- Cloud Screening to potentially increase science data return by 72% for EMIT
- Co-Adding permitting short integration time to avoid saturating the FPA
- **Fast (up to 8Gbps) and large (440Gbytes) radiation tolerant on-board storage**
- Downlink through Ethernet at 10Mbps (up to 100Mbps)
- **Low power 36 Watt** and Small Volume 290x180x50 mm
- Assembly structure based on Space VPX
- **Single Assembly providing C&DH and Application FSW/Firmware** for the full instrument including SSDR.
- **Radiation Tolerant Hardware** using SW/FW/System SEE mitigation (L1/L2 Cache disable, not use OCM, SEM IP (Scrubbing), Xilinx AXI bus firewall & RTP*, restart AppFSW/FW at each orbit
- **Modular OS/Software/Firmware architecture** portable to other applications (different OS, Interface (camera link, LVDS data out, smaller camera, optical communication), without SSDR)

Software & FPGA Debugging

Designed for debug:

- VxWorks IDE based interactive software debugger (over Ethernet or Serial), and Xilinx XSDK/Vitis SDK interactive debugging (over JTAG).
 - Allows to break into different threads and debugging them individually.
 - Was used extensively to debug VxWorks drivers (QSPI and Ethernet)
- Menu based** interactive mode for testing features.
 - Try things without rebuilding SW
- Build with **Debug Mode**
 - Journal Integrity checking on the SDDR SW.
 - Memory leak tracking (built into application)
 - TRON (tracing messages back to source code)
- Test cases integrate with Application FSW
 - Production testing
 - Hammer testing
 - Application testing
- FPGA debug with ILA insertion using Vivado Tools
 - All part of the Xilinx FPGA design flow.
- Physical access to boards for hardware probing and **XJtag**

Physical access to board XJtag

```

MPR Menu
-----
Select Factory SATA..... 1
Select Factory SDDR..... 2
Get Disk Info..... 3
Get Disk Info Hammer..... 4
Create Disk..... 5
Release Disk..... 6
Select Partition.....
Release Partition.....
Recover Partition.....
Erase Partition.....
Format Partition.....
Write Test.....
Random Write Test (4x).....
Random Write Test (128x).....
Report Partition Usage.....
Erase First Blob.....
Read Test.....
Fill Disk.....
Block Erase.....
Dump Journal.....
Traverse Journal Forward.....
Traverse Journal Backward.....
Journal Seek Forward.....
Journal Seek Backwards.....
Journal Read Forward.....
Journal Read Backwards.....
Store Journal pointer.....
Read Journal pointer.....
Set Journal pointer.....
-----
CFPIASoC Debug, Performance and Diagnostics
-----
Enter Register Read/Write Sub-menu..... 1
Enter Data Test Sub-menu..... 2
Show data flow..... 3
Enable FPA Output..... 4
Enable CLink Output..... 5
Source CLink from memory..... 6
Toggle FPA capture bank..... 7
Toggle CLink source bank..... 8
Disable FPA Emulation..... 9
Disable Stamp..... 0
Calibrate PRISM2 ADCs..... a
Capture FPA Data..... b
Reset CLink source data..... c
LVDS Data Menu..... d
Change FPA Dims (Current: 1280 x 328 x 32 )..... e
FPA Emu Padding (Current: 0.250 x 8.500 )..... f
Dump Serial Buffers..... g
Reset Deployment loop..... h
Test BILToBIP..... i
-----
payload write data. Queue State 0 Queue Size 1024
payload size from 1024 to 483840
0x00000000ec400000
0x00000000ec400000
0x00000000ec400000
0x0000000000000001
0x0000000000000000
0x00000000ec400000
0x0000000000000001
0x0000000000000000
0x00000000ec400000
0x0000000000000001
0x0000000000000000
0x00000000ec400000
0x00000000000076200
0x0000000000000000
0x0000000000000000
-----
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(50):Partition 1: pending write data. Queue State 0 Queue Size 1024
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(102):Partition 1: writing data to disk
/mpr/diskssdr.cpp(630):ssdrDmaIsrQueueWrite from 0x0000000000000000 to 0x00000000ec400000
/mpr/diskssdr.cpp(665):Erasing a Ultra Block at address 0x00000000ec400000
/mpr/diskssdr.cpp(683):Erasing of Ultra Block at address 0x00000000ec400000 finished.
/mpr/diskssdr.cpp(698):ssdrDmaIsrQueueWrite write size 0x000000000076200
/mpr/apartition_journal.cpp(93):Appending journal
/mpr/apartition_journal.cpp(110):Journal appended
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(267):qtTicket=0x0000000000000000 finished
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(234):m_eQueueState == QueueFlush
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(247):Flushing journal if needed.
/mpr/apartition_processqueue.cpp(259):Flush was needed.
/mpr/apartition_journal.cpp(118):Writing journal 1
-----
/datacard/dump.cpp(13):
-----
0xc      0x8      0x4      0x0
/datacard/dump.cpp(14):
0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000001
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000040
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000028
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000040
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000008
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000001
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000000
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000000
/datacard/dump.cpp(69): 0x00000000 00000000 00000000 00000000
-----
Debug Mode
-----
-----
Dataflow Test Menu
-----
1 Setup DownLink Destination to SSE (TCP)..... 1
2 Setup DownLink Destination to SSS..... 2
3 Cleanup DownLink Destination..... 3
4 Init Storage..... 4
5 Release Storage..... 5
6 Recover Raw Data..... 6
7 Erase Raw Data..... 7
8 Recover Compressed Data..... 8
9 Erase Compressed Data..... 9
0 Stop Recording Raw Worker..... 0
a Start Recording Raw Worker..... a
b Trigger Raw Recording..... b
c Finish Raw Recording..... c
d Stop DownLink Worker..... d
e Start DownLink Worker..... e
f Forward Compressed Data..... f
g Start Direct Raw DownLink..... g
h Stop Direct Raw DownLink..... h
i Trigger DownLink Transmit..... i
j Finish Transmit..... j
k Adjust transmit count and type..... k
l Start Direct Raw DownLink..... l
m Stop Direct Raw DownLink..... m
n Trigger DownLink Direct Transmit..... n
o Start Processing (Compression Flow) Workers..... o
p Stop Processing (Compression Flow) Workers..... p
q Start Processing (Compression Flow)..... q
r Finish Processing (Compression Flow)..... r
s Set Number of Raw Frames to Process..... s
t Read Storage MRAM..... t
u Read Storage Registers..... u
v Toggle Storage Compression..... v
w Toggle Code and Cloud Screening..... w
x More BILToBIP..... x
y Toggle Code and Cloud Screening..... y
z More DataFlow Test Menu Options..... z
0 Exit..... 0
-----
????? Select options:

```

Where did the FPIE-D come from?

- The FPIE-D was delivered by a Stork!

Where did the FPIE-D come from?

- JPL's FPIE-D group has worked with Alpha Data on a number of projects since 2014.

- The FPIE-D was not delivered by a Stork!

- Reusing, and **designing for re-use** has allowed the FPIE-D teams for spin design variants quickly, focusing project efforts on new components.

Summary of Key Verification Technologies

Many new verification technologies were utilized on EMIT to improve verification quality and speed leading to significantly fewer bugs in real hardware. The ProASIC and Zynq designs and testbenches are vastly different

ProASIC (Verilog)

- SystemVerilog/Universal Verification Methodology (UVM) Testbench
- Mentor UVM Framework Component Generator
- Mentor UVM Register Assistant for stimulus
- Correct Designs UVM Extended for checking infrastructure
- Questa Code Coverage

Zynq (VHDL SoC)

- VHDL Testbench
- OSVVM Randomization & Checking Library
- Mentor Questa for simulation
- Regression Management Script (Regress.py)
- Jenkins Nightly Build & Regressions

Zynq PL Testbench


```
### Regression Summary for coverage_cwiz_0 ###
DIR  CLOG  SLOG  UCDB  -  STAT  PASS  FAIL  LGCY  UNKN  RTLE
33   33   33    33  -   33    32    0    1    0    0
#####
```

Component	Status	Value
fpiea	LEGACY	
atom	PASSED	454335
atom_adc	PASSED	
atom_adc_single	PASSED	
atom_dac	PASSED	931475
dictionary	PASSED	3562765
dictionary_persist	PASSED	3562405
fpa_capture	PASSED	1248705
fpa_capture_by1	PASSED	446945
fpa_capture_by16	PASSED	2256665
fpa_capture_by16_decimate	PASSED	2258265
fpa_capture_by1_shift	PASSED	
fpa_capture_by2	PASSED	553025
fpa_capture_by2by1	PASSED	746815
fpa_capture_by32	PASSED	4186305
fpa_capture_by32_decimate	PASSED	4189825
fpa_capture_by4	PASSED	812585
fpa_capture_by4_decimate	PASSED	812745
fpa_capture_by4_shift	PASSED	814155
fpa_capture_by64	PASSED	8004215
fpa_capture_by64_decimate	PASSED	8010455
fpa_capture_by8	PASSED	1294445
fpa_capture_by8_decimate	PASSED	1281195
fpa_capture_long	PASSED	434545
fpa_emu	PASSED	386305
fpa_emu_gap	PASSED	371855
fpa_emu_half	PASSED	239225
fpa_emu_xy_start	PASSED	314815
fpa_overflow	PASSED	887855
hk_adc	PASSED	976735
hk_ping_pong	PASSED	5214265
ltc2271_adc	PASSED	1063265
reg	PASSED	

Mitigation of Zynq Radiation Effect

Resource	Total Rate/bit	Total Resources available	Total Resources available on XQ7Z100-RF1156-2i (FPIE-D 7z5)	EMIT Ressource utilization XQ7Z100-RF1156-2i (FPIE-D 7z5) (essential bits reported by VIVADO)	EMIT Resource Utilization of essential bits XQ7Z100-RF1156-2i (FPIE-D 7z5)	System Rate/device-day XQ7Z100-RF1156-2i (FPIE-D 7z5)	mean time to SEU event XQ7Z100-RF1156-2i (FPIE-D 7z5)	
Z7100							days	
Programmable Logic								
Configuration	1.88E-08	139,330,784	109,613,280	38,057,093	34.72%	9.11E-01	1.10	
BRAM	2.41E-07	27,832,320	27,832,320	6,340,608	22.78%	1.52E+00	0.66	
						Total:	2.44E+00	0.41
Processing System								
OCM	2.41E-07	2097152			0%	0.00E+00		
L1 D Cache	2.41E-07	524288			100%	6.30E-02	15.86	
L1 I Cache	2.41E-07	524288			100%	6.30E-02	15.86	
L2 Cache	2.41E-07	4194304			100%	5.04E-01	1.98	
Generic Processor SEFI	9.00E-03	2			100%	1.80E-02	55.56	
						Total:	6.48E-01	1.54

- **ProASIC** to provide a trusted layer
 - To receive commands from ISS via 1553
 - To control power switching sequence of EMIT avionic assemblies
 - To communicate and gather telemetry from EMIT avionic assemblies
 - To monitor current AUX for Zynq SEL events
 - watchdog for Zynq
 - Switch selection of the Zynq Flight Software and Firmware images in QSPI

- **Zynq components:**

- PS OCM (On-Chip Memory) is still used only at boot, but the timing window of vulnerability is so small, that utilization considered 0%
- PS Caches: Disable all L1 and L2 cache to eliminate SEUs in those areas.
- PL SEL: Monitor Zynq AUX current for detecting SEL events and Power Cycle Zynq device
- This leaves the Zynq 7100 specifically with three areas of SEE vulnerability:
 - **PL configuration bits.** An upset here can lead to loss of communication with ATOM, SDDR, and FPIE-A, preventing science data acquisition, data processing and hanging AXI DMA bus. It is mitigated through Xilinx Soft Error Mitigation IP (scrubbing), Xilinx AXI firewall IP and reloading Application FW by restarting the Application FSW at each orbit .
 - **PL BRAM.** BRAM is used mainly for buffering (FIFO) science data. An SEU here would only likely to corrupt science data.
 - **PS Generic Processor SEFI.** This could lead to a WachDogTimer reset, software reboot, and loss of thermal stability. Recovery time from each event is estimated at 3-7 days (2 days minimum for thermal recovery, the rest allocated to anomaly investigation).

Hardware Selections

	DEVICE RESOURCE AVAILABLE			DEVICE RESOURCE UTILIZATION of design with 3 compression cores	NUMBER OF DEVICE REQUIRED (70% utilization)	
Device Name	Xilinx Zynq Z-7100	Radiation-Hardened Space Grade Xilinx Virtex-5QV	Space grade RTG4 FPGA	Xilinx Zynq 7Z100	QV Virtex5 FPGA	RTG4 FPGA
Part Number	XQ7Z100	XQR5VFX130	RT4G150 (package CQ352)	XQ7Z100	XQR5VFX130	RT4G150 (package CQ352)
Programmable Logic						
Look-Up Tables (Slice LUTs)	277400	81920	50608	76.88%	4	7
Flip-Flops (Slice Registers)	554800	81920	50608	37.08%	4	6
Extensible Block RAM [# 36 Kb Blocks]	755	298	650	30.28%	2	1
Programmable DSP Slices (18x25 MACCs)	2020	320	462	15.44%	2	1

- Zynq provides
 - Programmable Logic large enough to accommodate designs with 3 flex compression cores (See Table)
 - Dual Core processors for C&DH Flight Software and Application Flight Software
 - Co-location on same device of Flight Software and Firmware reduce interface complexity between the processor and programmable logic
 - Reduce manufacture challenge
 - Reduce Size, Weight and Power
- SSDR provides
 - large 440 GB to store raw and compressed data
 - Fast write/read data rate SRIO for data acquisition from focal plane array
- DDR3 provides scratch pads for data acquisition, and data processing
- Space VPX Backplane provides SRIO interface to storage device SSDR

- FPE-D consists of
 - 3 components
 - *FPIE-D processor card*
 - *One 2-slot VPX backplane*
 - *SSDR (solid state drive)*
 - PWB form factor: custom (280mm x 170mm)
- Electrical interfaces
 - Various D-Sub and Smiths Interconnect SpaceVPX connectors
- Dry-mounted on underside to sensor shelf with 12 M5 screws into inserts
- Total mass is approximately: 3.4 kg
- Thermal dissipation: 44 W

Mercury SSDR

Handling complexity

- Already mentioned the SoC is complex!
- How did we quickly design a system that complex?
- **Modularity**
 - Easy to understand. Enables splitting up development work
- **Abstraction and Interfacing**
 - Lets us swich between breadboard and real board
 - Lets us swich between storage technology (SATA/SSDR)
- **Designing for re-use**
 - Much of the code from heritage projects could be re-used
 - EMIT was designed for the future re-use

